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VALUE BASED EDUCATION

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Abstract:

This paper describes the “value based Learning” and what is value education. The common learning is only depending on text book. The teacher’s teaching on curriculum in classroom. But the purpose is only examination view. This paper tries to discuss some activities for value of our national needs and national achievements. In this paper there are concept of value education and role of teacher in value education. Present paper tries to discuss normal learning and how we can include value in education. Just as the teacher will have to learn new techniques for implicate value education in day to day learning.

Key words: *The use of value based Learning in our curricula.*

Concept of value:

We today; use the term value as ‘Literary value,’ ‘Democratic Value’, ‘Life Value’ and ‘Education value in our day to day speaking and writing. In life process man accepts good things and avoids bad things. It is not human living to act neutrally and in the light of witness only. Acceptable and non-acceptable, good and bad are the nature of values. Values are established and they are practicable. They can be achieved. Indian culture is based on the values, kind heartedness, self control, universal brotherhood, honesty, respect to others and faith. Due to deterioration of these values, new values like indiscipline and destructive mentality came into existence.

Role of Education:

Education is the potential instrument to bring about purposeful behavioral changes in the individual. It helps to achieve social integration by alleviating social prejudices and by creating a strong desire for a rational social order. Education should aim at achieving personal integration by developing integrated personality of the individual and by inculcating right values, scientific temper of mind, right attitudes, productive imagination and creative intelligence. Education should develop cultural awakening, cultural understanding and appreciation, so as to transmit cultural values for promotion of cultural integration. Education should inculcate national ideals and true patriotic outlook to pave way for the promotion of emotional integration.

Role of Value Education

Value education as an indispensable part of one’s Endeavour at self-identification by means of self-enquiry, self-analysis and self-evaluation. Such type of education for values, therefore, necessitates an approach that harmonizes the essential components contributing to the growth and development of personality. The role of education in understanding and appreciating the self in relation to others and the Divine self itself encapsulates the essence of values. The learner must identify within himself the positive values that lead him to recrystallize his vision of fullness, and the negative ones standing in way of his advancement. He must explore and

examine each value-concept in term of Truth, Goodness and Beauty Therein lies the genesis of value-education.

Let the students use their Head, Heart and Hands!

- Activities using their Head – Solving riddles and puzzles, Dramatization, Role play, Discussions and debates etc.
- Activities using their Heart – Music, Games, etc.
- Activities using their hands – Drawing illustrations and coloring, poster making, making models and collages, craft work etc, And many more!

The role of the Teacher:

As a substitute mother and a role model should have a positive, healthy attitude and the right values. A balanced emotional outlook a regulated mind which is able to think clearly and answer without any ambiguity should help the students achieve their full potential and bring out the best in them. Be able to lead them towards a better tomorrow. The teachers must an important role in value education. The most important aspect is they should set good examples of conduct and behavior which the students may imbibe in them.

Activities:

Proper reforms in curriculum should be made from the point of view of our national needs and national achievements.

1. Common prayers and observations of religious festivals in the educational institutions.
2. Avoiding comments on casteism or communalism in the classroom.
3. Conducting a short course on national literature.
4. Encouraging the study of one of the Indian languages other than the regional language.
5. Arranging co-curricular activities centering on human understanding.
6. Organizing National ceremonies, symbols, songs, national pledges, etc.

7. Compiling a short anthology of songs in all languages for wide circulation.
8. Emphasizing the points of interdependence cooperation and integration by way of educational programmes.
9. Encouraging the participation of people of different castes and religions in national fairs and festivals.
10. Organizing dramas, seminars, debates and discussions advocating the concept of national harmony.
11. Increasing use of mass media for harnessing national unity.
12. Revising textbooks so as to emphasize national unity and love of the country.

Conclusion:

We live with proper values than our and society's development become proper. All round development of students is possible through value education. Students are the part of society, and our education system also for this society. Education should foster universal and eternal values, oriented towards the unity and integration of our people. Such value education should help eliminate obscurantism, religious fanaticism, violence, superstition and fatalism. Value education has a profound positive content, based on our cultural heritage, national goals and universal perceptions.

Values-based Education is a great success and is one of the fastest growing approaches in the world, endorsed by teachers, school leaders and governments. This is because it is based on the soundest principles of pedagogy, educational philosophy, brain research and common sense. It helps pupils to develop holistically, nurturing a secure sense of self, respect for self and others and supports the raising of academic standards.

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